

Proposed Improved Marketing Communication Strategy, To Boost Awareness and Enhance Sales of PT Leo Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: With the tagline of “Connecting empty dining tables with empty stomachs,” LEO (disguised name) provides a food service platform where customers can reserve restaurant tables and get timely-based discounts through yield management. By getting customers to dine in during odd-eating hours, restaurants get to recoup its operating expenses. However, even with this seemingly win-win situation for all stakeholders, LEO has not been able to be as successful as they should be. This study aims to find out the cause of this low adoption rate, as well as the solution to further boost sales and overall performance of LEO Indonesia. Data collection is done through desk research, previous studies, a questionnaire to customers, an interview with the employee, and some limited internal data. Further in-depth analysis was conducted using 5 As Customer Path and Integrated Marketing Communication. This revealed that the root cause to LEO’s slowdown after their initial success, was the fact that they were focusing so much on customer retention and not enough on customer acquisition anymore. Having found the root cause, a strategy formulation was created using the ERRC Grid framework. These frameworks provided solutions for all the factors mentioned above, while focusing a lot more on LEO’s marketing strategy to increase brand awareness, adoption rate, and overall performance, since the service that LEO have been offering manages to fit the wants and needs of current and potential customers.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Customer Path, Food Services, Integrated Marketing Communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Everybody eats. With a population of 273.5 million, coupled with rising incomes in being the third fastest growing economy in the Group of Twenty (G20) and the fastest growing tourism sector in South-East Asia (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2022), Indonesia is a highly desirable market for many businesses, including food services. Indonesia’s middle class is also among the fastest expanding compared to neighboring Southeast Asian countries, where 80% of the population who were poor in 1993 moved over the poverty line by 2014 (Chavez, 2020). Services constitute 38% of total GDP, where the most important contributors include trade, hotel and restaurants, which accounts for around a total of 14% of Indonesia’s GDP. The Indonesian food services industry was valued at USD 24.3 billion in 2020 (USDA), making it the largest market in Southeast Asia. PT Let’s Eat Out (LEO) was founded and co-founded by C. and K. in 2013, as a company that owns and operates a reservation platform for users who are looking for a better dining experience, at more affordable prices. Headquartered in Bangkok, they operate with around 100 - 200 employees across 12 locations, and a revenue of around USD 15 - 25 million per year. LEO is in a Series B round of funding, having acquired a total funding of USD25.5 million, the last one being USD10 million in July 2018 (Craft.co, 2022). As an effort of expansion, LEO Indonesia was launched in 2019. Unlike the popular discounts that are being provided by online delivery services, LEO is not simply burning money in providing these discounts. Instead, the restaurants are given the freedom to create their own discount schemes using yield management, where discounts are little to none during busy lunch and dinner hours, but a lot during odd-eating hours. By redirecting traffic to these times, it would help restaurants in recouping some of their, otherwise, wasted operating expenses. LEO had a high initial success, and customers started seeing the benefit of making reservations through LEO’s website and application. However, when Covid-19 reached Indonesia on March 2020, interest in LEO Indonesia users was already at an all-time low by April 2020 (Figure 1). Movement restrictions programs and the economic slowdown meant that previous LEO users now prefer to cook at home or take advantage of online delivery services instead. However, initial analysis also revealed that the decreasing interest has happened since before the pandemic, around August 2019 to be exact, which was only a mere 8 months after the initial launch of LEO Indonesia. Therefore, this research is aimed to find out the factors that cause LEO Indonesia to not be as successful as the neighboring countries, and how to overcome them.

Figure 0. Interest in LEO Indonesia Over Time (Number of Downloads, Clicks, Searchers, etc.)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is critical to firstly develop the conceptual framework for this research (Figure 2), which will become beneficial in determining the correct steps in developing an improved strategy for LEO, to further increase their customer base, brand awareness and sales in Indonesia. There are two frameworks that are going to be used for analysis, namely 5 As Customer Path, Integrated Marketing Communication, and ERRC Grid.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

2.1 5 AS CUSTOMER PATH MODEL FRAMEWORK

Today’s customers of the modern age tend to be more actively connected with each other, in search of the ones with higher knowledge and experiences, to help each other find the answers to any further questions after these first touch points. This forms what is called the ask-and-advocate relationships between customers, and can make or break the brand’s initial appeal, depending on any preferences during the conversation. Hence, it is important to assess this path through Kotler’s (2017) 5As model of Aware, Appeal, Ask, Act, and Advocate.

2.2 INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS

The reach of the message of the company has become a fundamental aspect of its effective marketing strategy, and aids in reaching the goals and brand equity of the company itself (Cvetkov et al, 2019). The strategic process to decide, develop, implement, assess, and coordinate throughout all stakeholders within an organization for a given period, is known as integrated marketing communications (Belch, 2007). Today’s integrated marketing communication tools have the additional benefit from social media, as well as digital marketing, that has been proven to be a lot more effective than other tools of olden days (Kuswaha et al, 2020).

2.3 ERRC GRID

The ERRC Grid is an analytic tool developed by Chan Kim and Renée Mauborgne (2005) to drive companies to focus simultaneously on Eliminating and Reducing, as well as Raising and Creating while unlocking a new blue ocean. However, this

Four Actions Framework in general also helps address LEO’s brand awareness issues, and improve overall performance of LEO, by arranging the factors within a simpler 2x2 matrix.

3. METHODOLOGY

An in-depth interview with LEO’s employee, desk research, literature study and all sorts of secondary data were used to provide the qualitative data, as the researcher had no access to LEO’s internal data. Meanwhile, the quantitative method is carried out using an online questionnaire in the form of a Google Form, which was distributed on January 1st, 2022. First and foremost is to identify the problems that are going to be analyzed more in-depth to become the business issue, by gathering as much information as possible through the observation of LEO’s service through their websites, previous studies and analysis about LEO, as well as the researcher’s experience during the time of his work there. Other online sources were also used to gain better insights for external analysis using 5 As Customer Path and Integrated Marketing Communication frameworks. The ERRC grid is chosen to help convey these strategies and implementation plans more clearly, by applying drive to the company on Eliminating, Reducing, Raising and Creating values.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 BUSINESS ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

The preliminary attractiveness of a brand is greatly manipulated by the community that surrounds the customer to determine the behavior in the current connectivity era. What should have been seemingly personal decisions, have become social decisions. In this era, too, loyalty has a definite translation to become the eagerness in promoting a brand. For example, a customer may no longer need to repurchase a specific brand of products or services or may not be able to do so due to unavailability of products or services in certain locations. However, if the customer has been satisfied with the products or services from the brand, they might continue to recommend it even though they are no longer using it.

Figure 3. The 5 As Customer Path Model Framework

Speaking of brand understanding, today’s customers of the modern age tend to be more actively connected with each other, in search of the ones with higher knowledge and experiences, to help each other find the answers to any further questions after these first touch points. This forms what is called the ask-and-advocate relationships between customers, and can make or break the brand’s initial appeal, depending on any preferences during the conversation. Hence, it is important to assess this path through Kotler’s (2017) 5As model of Aware, Appeal, Ask, Act, and Advocate (Figure 3).

4.1.1 AWARE

Most customers’ journeys begin at a point where they are forced to submissively be exposed to many other brands during this awareness stage, resulting from previous experiences, marketing communications, and advocacies from other brands. A customer

who had previously encountered a certain brand will most probably be able to recognize and recall it, hence why company-driven advertising is considered significant bases for brand awareness, along with word-of-mouth from other more knowledgeable and experienced customers (Kotler et al., 2017).

Figure 4. Customers' Awareness of Food Services Providers in Indonesia

Out of the 113 total respondents, 92.9% have heard, experienced, and/or used food services prior to the survey, and only 7.1% of them are not aware or familiar. Out of those that answered yes, the next question asked was "If the answer to the previous question was 'Yes', which food service providers do you know?". To this, respondents were given 7 different options they can choose from, to eliminate any online delivery food services providers, as they are not considered as direct competitors to LEO. Respondents were also asked to choose up to 3 service providers that they know, including an "others" option that they can put on their own. The findings are as follow (Figure 4).

Figure 5. Respondents' Awareness to Food Services Providers' Brands (Outside of Online Deliveries)

Zomato had the highest level of brand awareness, being voted by 91.4% of the, now, 105 respondents. Considering that Traveloka Eats is considered new in the food services industry, they were doing well being recognized by 80% of the respondents. Came in as the third most recognized, was Google Reviews, being voted by 64.8% of the respondents. With 36.2% respondents being aware, Qraved is also considered as quite recognizable. A close fourth most recognized service provider is Fave, having been voted by 28.6% of the respondents. LEO is quite low in terms of brand awareness from respondents, only getting 21.9% of votes. Meaning that from a total of 92 respondents who have had experiences in using food services, only 23 of them are aware of the existence of LEO. Chope, the one with the most similar business model to LEO, receives an even slightly lower of awareness from respondents, with 19% of votes. In the 'others' option: 2% say they are also aware of another service provider called Pergikuliner.com, and 1 respondent put in GrabFood and GoFood, but is disregarded as online delivery food services are not the focus of this questionnaire.

4.1.2 APPEAL

Figure 6. Factors that Make LEO Appealing to Customers

According to the earlier interview with the county lead of LEO Indonesia, there are 7 main aspects that LEO claims to have competitive advantage over its competitors, and the respondents were asked to rate these aspects according to their likeness on a 5-scale rating: Very disliked, disliked, neutral, liked, and very liked (Figure 6). At first glance, none of the services that LEO provides, have been voted very disliked or disliked, except for the quantity and variety of merchants and restaurants being provided on the app. However, to get a better understanding, the researcher calculated the total score of each of the 7 categories (Table 1).

Table 1. Scoring System to the Factors that Make LEO Appealing to Customers

Categories	Very Disliked (-2)		Disliked (-1)		Neutral (0)		Liked (+1)		Very Liked (+2)		Total Score
	Votes	Score	Votes	Score	Votes	Score	Votes	Score	Votes	Score	
Ease of use of the application and/or website	0	0	0	0	10	0	12	12	1	2	14
Getting discounted prices	0	0	0	0	5	0	9	9	9	18	27
No complicated terms and conditions	0	0	0	0	7	0	9	9	7	14	23
No subscription fees	0	0	0	0	8	0	9	9	6	12	21
Can make a specific reservation by the hour and number of diners	0	0	0	0	10	0	11	11	2	4	15
Can browse through photos, ambience, reviews, and ratings	0	0	0	0	8	0	11	11	4	8	19
Quantity and variety of merchants / restaurants	0	0	2	-2	12	0	5	5	4	8	11

Getting discounted prices are what respondents really like the most about using LEO, with 0% of the respondents voting very disliked and disliked, 21.7% are neutral, 39.1% liked, 39.1% really like it, giving it a total score of 27. Respondents also liked the fact that LEO does not have any complicated terms and conditions, giving it a total score of 23. No respondents claimed to very disliked or disliked it, 30.4% were neutral, a majority 39.1% liked it, and another 30.4% really liked it. The third most liked feature of LEO is the fact that, unlike some of its competitors, customers do not have to endure subscription fees, where none of the respondents voted very disliked and disliked, 34.8% are neutral about it, a majority of 39.1% like it, 26.1% really liked it, and a total score of 21. Fourth, was giving customers the ability to browse through detailed photos, ambience, menu, reviews, ratings, etc., with a total score of 19. No respondents voted very disliked and disliked, 34.8% were only neutral about it, 47.8% said they liked it, and 17.4% really liked it a lot. Being able to make specified reservations by the hour, as well as by the number of diners, is the fifth most appealing aspect of LEO, with a total score of 15. None of the respondents voted it to be very disliked and disliked, 43.5% were just neutral, 47.8% really liked it, and 8.7% really liked it. Next was the ease of use of LEO’s website and/or application, getting a total score of 14. Like most other aspects, no respondents very disliked and disliked the user friendliness, 43.5% claim to be neutral, a majority of 52.2% of the respondents say they like it, and even 4.3% respondents still say they really like it. With a total score of only 11, the quantity and variety of restaurants available on the app is that is most disliked by customers. While none of the respondents voted very disliked, 8.7% of them voted that they somewhat disliked this aspect and would perhaps prefer more options of restaurants. A major 52.2% say they were neutral about it, 21.7% voted for liked, and still a 17.4% voted for really liked.

4.1.3 ASK

By this stage, customers have already been stimulated by the curiosity to research the brands in a more aggressive and enthusiastic manner. Customers tend to draw on information from the online or offline media, friends, family, influencers, or even straight from the brands in the form of customer service centers or sales representatives, regarding the product or services in question (Kotler et al., 2017). This set of advice will enable customers to make further informed decisions.

Figure 7. Respondent's Answer on Whether or Not They Know the Uniqueness of LEO

Out of the 90 respondents who have not previously used LEO before, all 100% of them do not know what LEO is (Figure 2.23). They never came across it, and do not have any lead of information about it. This may be due to the lack of marketing on LEO's end, and the inactivity within their social media that has not been replying to potential customers' questions or even simply making informative posts about their services. The best possible way to find further communication is through its 'Chat with Us' feature (Figure 2.24) on the website and application, and that alone, is not enough in this modern technology era.

4.1.4 ACT

Here, it is vital to know that the customers' actions are not necessarily limited to the purchase of the products or services. Typically, it is possible for customers to have a deeper and further interaction with the brand after purchasing, using, and experiencing it, including things like after sales services. Therefore, brands should make sure to engage with their customers, to a point where they know surely that the overall ownership and user experience is positive and memorable. When brands receive issues or complaints from customers, they must pay attention and resolve these issues before it becomes public (Kotler et al., 2017).

EFFECTS OF COVID-19 ON CUSTOMER'S BEHAVIORS

Seeing how the interest in LEO reached its lowest point by April 2020, it is important to see whether the Covid-19 that reached Indonesia in March 2020 was the main cause of that, or if there are other major factors than Covid-19. The respondents were asked several behavioral questions that compare their eating out habits before, and during the Covid-19 pandemic. When asked how much of the respondents' monthly incomes are spent on eating out (Figure 8), there were higher levels of monthly spending between IDR 500.001 to IDR 4.000.000 before the pandemic, with the following breakdown. 3.6% of the respondents admit to spending less than IDR 500.000 per month to eat out before the Covid-19 pandemic, which increased to 20.5% during the pandemic, the 25.9% who spent IDR 500.000 to 1.000.000, also increased to 27.7%, a majority of 35.7% spend IDR 1.000.001 to 2.000.000, which became 36.7% during the pandemic, the 30.4% of respondents who spent IDR 2.000.001 to 4.000.000 before the pandemic, however, decreased to only 13.4% during the pandemic, the 4.5% that previously spent IDR 4.000.001 to 8.000.000, went down to 1.8%, and 0% spent more than IDR 8.000.000 before, and also during the pandemic. Even though many respondents still spend around the region of IDR 1.000.001 to 2.000.000, the overall monthly spending on eating out seem to decrease a little bit.

Figure 8. Respondents' Monthly Spending on Eating Out

Referring to the bigger picture conveyed by figure 9 below, the monthly frequency of respondents dining also went down. The majority that used to eat out 6 to 10 times a month before the pandemic, now only eat out 3 to 5 times a month, with the following breakdown. 3.5% of the 113 respondents ate out less than 3 times a month before Covid-19 and increased to 33.9% during the pandemic. Before the pandemic, 28.3% of the respondents ate out 3 to 5 times a month. This number increases to 48.7% during the pandemic. The biggest decrease can be seen in the number of respondents who eat out 6 to 10 times a month, from 39.8% before, to only 13.3% during Covid-19. The 21.2% that used to eat out 11 to 20 times before Covid-19, also went down to a mere 2.7% during Covid-19. 6.2% of the respondents that ate out around 21 to 30 times before the pandemic, decreased to a measly 1.8%, and the 0.9% that ate out more than 30 times, decreased to 0% during the pandemic.

Figure 9. Respondents' Monthly Frequency of Eating Out

Narrowing the focus down to the effect of Covid-19 on the operations of LEO, this next question asked, “How often do you book or reserve a table before coming to the restaurant?” to the 113 respondents (Figure 10). 52.2% of the respondents say that they only occasionally reserve even before the pandemic, probably since there are so many other restaurants in/around JABODETABEK. If customers do not get a table in the desired table, they can simply move to other nearby restaurants.

Surprisingly, even during the current pandemic, a majority of 46.0% of the respondents still only occasionally reserve a table beforehand. Even when the containment of the virus has been getting better and restaurants are back to normal operations, the amount and frequency of people have not gone back up. Even the 15.9% of respondents who had never made a reservation before Covid-19, increased to 23.0%. This could be caused by other behavioral or economic factors, that causes the frequency of people eating out to go down, hence the restaurants are empty and people still no longer need to make bookings or reservations.

However, there are also increases in the more frequent side of the options. The 16.8% who frequently made reservations before Covid-19, have now increased to 20.4%; the 7.1% who very frequently made reservations have increased to 8.0%; and even the small percentage of the 0.9% who had always made reservations before the pandemic, have also increased to 2.7%. This might be due to customers wanting to know more about the safety of going to the restaurant, before being there, to take the extra action to keep them and their loved ones safer.

Figure 10. Respondents' Frequency of Reserving a Table Before Going to the Restaurant

In this phase, customers start to develop certain behaviors based on all the communications they were exposed to in the aware phase above, usually by creating short-term memory, augmenting long-term memory, and become appealed to a smaller number of brands. Memorable brands that leave amazing impressions are more receptive, as they are more likely to enter, and rise to these potential customers' short lists, hence brand appeal must be made strong in any competitive industries (Kotler et al., 2017).

4.1.5 ADVOCATE

It is possible for customers to become loyal to specific brands over time, causing them to retent, repurchase, reuse, and eventually, advocate to other potential customers. If, in the Act stage, customers really enjoyed the experience of the products or services, they may advocate and recommend by sharing positive stories and feedback to others. On top of that, if others have negative reactions regarding the advocacy and that customer feels obligated to defend the brands they care about, this is called brand loyalty. The higher number of advocates, and loyal advocates, a brand has, the more willing customers are to recommend the brand, hence also the more likely they are to purchase the goods or services again in the future (Kotler et al., 2017).

Figure 11. Where Respondents Find Out about LEO

Apart from the majority 52.2% of respondents having first heard about LEO from social media, it seems like word of mouth is the second highest contribution, being voted by 26.1% of the respondents. Hence, this means that they have felt the benefits from the previous stages so much that they decided to tell their friends, colleagues, family and/or relatives about LEO, for them to also feel the benefit as well. This is quite a big success, also proving that there is not much to fix about the services being offered by LEO but is also a little worrying since their integrated marketing communications are either not reaching the target audience, or simply have not been done to its maximum potential.

4.2 ROOT CAUSE ANALYSIS

The reach of the message of the company has become a fundamental aspect of its effective marketing strategy, and aids in reaching the goals and brand equity of the company itself (Cvetkov et al, 2019). The strategic process to decide, develop, implement, assess, and coordinate throughout all stakeholders within an organization for a given period, is known as integrated marketing

communications (Belch, 2007). Today’s integrated marketing communication tools have the additional benefit from social media, as well as digital marketing, that has been proven to be a lot more effective than other tools of olden days (Kuswaha et al, 2020).

Figure 12. 8 Major Marketing Communication

4.2.1 ADVERTISING

Based on the interview conducted with B. L., and the researcher’s own experience, there has been little to no offline advertising done by LEO. The questionnaire also supported this matter, where none of the respondents have seen any form of offline advertisements on newspaper, magazines, billboards, brochures, etc. In fact, LEO’s only effort was to provide all merchants with a 160cm x 60cm standing x-banner to be displayed in the front of their restaurants, to mainly let customers know that the restaurant is available for reservations with discounts on their app. As for the online advertisements, there are no records of any other apart from the product placement advertisements on Youtube, which was the main source of traffic when LEO endorsed several influential Indonesian food vloggers. This includes the likes of Ken & Grat, MGDALENAF, Tanboy Kun, and Paopao, who are verified and have a massive following on Youtube. LEO’s service speaks for itself after that, and the traffic started rolling in. However, there has not been any other endorsed videos after 2019, hence why the hype may no longer exist. As for other advertisements in other offline and online platforms, there has been no recollection of them neither from the questionnaire, nor the interview, as well as the researcher’s personal experience as a customer and ex-employee. If LEO achieved their early success purely from advertising through endorsements of other Youtubers, it can be safe to say that they would have an even bigger success today if they were to try other forms of advertisements like magazine, newspaper, television, radio, billboard, poster, brochure, direct selling, cross selling, etc.

4.2.2 SALES PROMOTION

LEO creates sales promotions where customers get special discounts or vouchers, on top of the discount they are already getting, when booking through the LEO application or website during special days of the year. These marketing campaigns, though, can only be seen through their social media, or the in-app push notifications for those customers who have downloaded the app previously. Hence, it is not reaching the bigger target market of appealing to the newer customer base. However, these promotions are still being done actively on a regular basis since the beginning of LEO’s launch, until today.

4.2.3 EVENTS AND EXPERIENCE

There are proofs of LEO throwing several events and experiences, done in restaurants of their merchants. They held open talk shows, press conferences, and presentations that answer what, who, when, and where questions that some of the public may have about LEO. These events were usually attended by the CEO and other board members, who specifically flew in from LEO in other parts of the world, to deliver their vision, mission, and goals of what LEO Indonesia means for the future. However, like the rest of LEO

Indonesia’s marketing efforts, the last reported event was held in 2019, and there have been no events and experiences being held afterwards.

4.2.4 PR AND PUBLICITY

LEO Indonesia has not had any Public Relations or Publicity figure that represents their brand, since it was first launched in 2019 until the day this research was conducted. Even though LEO has previously endorsed several Youtubers for product placement in their food vlogs, they do not have the luxury of having one specific public figure that continues to promote their services on a day-to-day basis.

4.2.5 ONLINE AND SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING

Up to the time this research is being conducted and completed, LEO Indonesia’s active social media pages are as follows: Their most active is the @LEO.indonesia verified Facebook page, with 639.473 followers. Even though the latest post was in August 2022, most posts get little to no likes or comments. Like Facebook, @LEO_id is also a verified page that customers can find on Instagram, with around 16.000 followers, 210 posts, an average of 10 to 15 likes per post, and most posts only get 0 to 2 comments that were never replied. On Twitter, LEO Indonesia is not verified, only has 63 followers, with only 38 Tweets, and the latest Tweet was in December 2020. On Youtube, LEO Indonesia does not have its specific channel, but instead shares one with LEO worldwide, only with around 800 subscribers, relatively low numbers of viewers, and the latest video was uploaded 3 years ago. @LEO_id can also be found on TikTok (Figure 2.45. It is not verified, only has 2 followers, and has not posted any videos to this date. Like Youtube, LEO has a shared worldwide page on LinkedIn, with around 21.000 followers. Their last post was in June 2022, on average gets around 10 to 20 likes, and a couple of comments at best that are never replied to.

4.2.6 MOBILE MARKETING

As far as mobile marketing is concerned, LEO has always been very reliant on their push notification on mobile phones of customers that have previously downloaded the LEO app. This is considered as one of the most affordable ways of marketing since there is no additional cost. Push notifications are aimed highly on customer retention, where LEO users will get notified of new marketing campaigns, new merchant restaurants, and other discounts information. This has also been done continuously on a day-to-day basis but is purely effective for customer retention and not new customer acquisition.

4.2.7 DIRECT AND DATABASE MARKETING

There has been no record of LEO conducting direct and database marketing up to the point of this research, and there were no recalls of it from the questionnaire to customers, interview with country lead, and the researcher’s experience as a customer, as well as an ex-employee.

4.2.8 PERSONAL SELLING

The only personal selling being done by LEO, is towards their merchant acquisition. The business development team are the ones going out and approaching restaurants, to give a sales pitch of LEO’s business model, to try and get them interested in becoming LEO’s merchants along with its benefits. However, there is no personal selling being done on the customers side, on record.

4.3 PROPOSED STRATEGY

Table 2 ERCC Grid

Eliminate	Raise
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving out free service charges. • Giving the option for merchants to drop out at any time they wish. • Eat-to-Go service. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer acquisition. • Facebook and Instagram advertisements. • Followers and engagements on social media.
Reduce	Create
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The flat service charge rate of IDR 35.000 per diners in all restaurants. • Putting too much focus on endorsing Indonesian 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TikTok account. • Expansions to other cities outside of JABODETABEK.

<p>food vloggers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of Business Development employees. ● Customer retention. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Offline events and experiences. ● Television and radio advertisements. ● Billboards, banners, flyers, and brochures. ● E-wallet payment options.
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4.3.1 ELIMINATE

The questionnaire shows that the food service that LEO delivers do not only appeal to the younger and tech-savvy generation, but throughout all generations and levels of the population. After all, everybody is always looking to be thrifty and saving money, and LEO is the only one who provides this kind of service and experience for customers looking to dine-in, whereas most are focusing on the delivery services sector. Considering Indonesia's huge numbers of population and available restaurants, there would be untouched potential markets if LEO was to continue focusing on their smaller STP. They should try to target all generations and social classes of the Indonesian market, help more restaurants, as well as LEO itself, to become more profitable. The availability and variety of restaurants that have become LEO's merchants have also been the complaint of customers, saying that there are not enough options. According to the interview with B. L., the problem does not only lay in acquiring new merchants, but also the dropouts of existing merchants who do not see the benefit in joining LEO. The contract should have a say as to how long a merchant should stay, before they can choose to leave, since it may not be obvious enough that LEO's business model only becomes profitable in the long run. If the contract bonded restaurants to stay as merchants for a longer period, they would start seeing the benefit of becoming a merchant, and to hopefully stay longer. Furthermore, this would even generate word-of-mouth among restaurant owners, which would also help with bringing inbound traffic of new merchants. In the past, B. L. also stated that he had to sign off on giving restaurants free service charges for the first 50 to 100 customers, to get restaurants to try and become merchants with no strings attached. Not only did this take away from LEO's profitability, but it also meant that merchants would be able to take advantage of this free service charges and can simply leave LEO once the offer was up. With a binding contract, paired with the right IMC to both customers and merchants, this can also be reduced simply by increasing the inbound traffic instead. In fact, it may also be a good idea to start a referral program for merchants too. As the spread of the Covid-19 becomes more contained, and businesses, as well as the economy, have started to go back to normal, it might be time to terminate the Eat-to-Go service that LEO started providing in March 2020. It was a good idea to get customers to still use their services, but even then, they were still beaten by online delivery food services. Furthermore, LEO's focus has always been on providing discounts for the dine-in customers. They would lose their biggest competitive advantage if they were to continue putting resources towards their Eat-to-Go services, considering that there are bigger and better market leaders within that specific type of food services industry. It would also confuse the customers, especially since LEO's tagline is "Connecting Empty Dining Tables, with Empty Stomachs."

4.3.2 RAISE

There have also been previous complaints where reservations do not come true to the merchants, and customers do not end up getting the desired time and discount of their initial reservation. This would generate bad reviews and publicity of LEO's services from both the customers and the merchants, hence they should always continue making updates within their App and Website to fix any errors and bugs. Furthermore, this is highly important as LEO already does not have a large following in social media, and a couple of bad reviews can surely ruin their reputation. However, LEO's two most active social media platforms are its Facebook and Instagram page. They should be able to start with the advertising services provided, not only to increase awareness, but also towards traffic, engagement, and business leads. In fact, Instagram is now a part of Facebook, where the ads manager is combined into one, and can target specific audience according to location, demographics, interests, behaviors, custom audiences, and lookalike audiences with very reasonable prices that can be adapted to LEO's budgeting. With a CPC or cost-per-click of USD 0.20 to USD 2, CPM or cost-per-impressions of USD 6.70 per 1000 impressions, and CPE or cost-per-engagement of USD 0.01 to USD 0.05 per engagement, advertisements on Facebook alone have been proven to reaching almost any age group, while Instagram excels when it comes to reaching the 25 to 29 years old audience. By raising higher click-through rates (CTRs), advanced targeting options, generating sales with higher order values, and higher engagements, not only will it increase customers' call-to-actions (CTAs), but also the general social media following. Awareness, interaction, and engagement should also be of LEO's focus on raising, towards the public. Even though a product and/or service is as good as it sounds, customers would not see the benefit if they have not tried

it, let alone heard of it. In this modern and technology-advanced era, most first interactions that customers have with businesses are through their online social media. Hence, it is important to keep these social media platforms active, to try to not only raise awareness to potential customers, but also interact and engage with current customers. Social media will also help LEO to better market, promote, and advertise its services.

4.3.3 REDUCE

The flat IDR35.000 rate that LEO charges to all merchants for every person that they bring in, also limits the chances of getting more new merchants. LEO should try changing it to a percentage basis, so lower-tier restaurants will be interested in becoming merchants. For example, the IDR 35.000 service charge may not seem big to restaurants where the average bill per person is around IDR 200.000 - 250.000, but it would seem too steep for restaurants with IDR 50.000 - 100.000 average bill for them to endure. Even though changing to a percentage basis may seem to lower LEO's profitability, it would increase the number of merchants, leading to an increase in customers, hence also an increase in reservation and transactions. To also leave more room in the marketing budget, it may also be a good idea to reduce the number of its business development employees. With the correct marketing strategy, it may be possible to have more inbound traffic of restaurants that would be interested in joining LEO, rather than having up to 20 BDs at a time to set up meetings and try to convince new potential merchants. This also means it would increase efficiency and productivity of the company, by putting the available resources into reaching the goal better. By putting the already limited budget to only endorsing Indonesia's influential Youtube food vloggers, means that there is no budget left to do other marketing in other channels. Granted, LEO's current strategy seemed to succeed in initially bringing great market response in the first place, but the hype seemed to have died out a while ago as shown by the decreasing interest. LEO Indonesia should try broadening its marketing strategy by trying other platforms, including some physical offline ones.

4.3.4 CREATE

Offline events have also been proven to be effective in showing customers, especially the older generations, that LEO truly and physically exists. Take Jenius, for example, where in their early release days, they would set up pop-up booths in many shopping malls to get customers familiarized with the product. On top of that, the sales representatives are also able to get new users to sign up on the spot in exchange for some giveaways and cashbacks, and make the process slightly easier than having to sign up for the online app. Having launched in 2016, Jenius already had 2.7 million active users by 2020 (CNBC Indonesia, 2020). LEO may also try the same method, where customers can directly use the app to get discounts in merchants' restaurants within the same shopping malls. One of LEO's indirect competitors, GoFood from Gojek, also chooses their offline marketing events by organizing many offline Food Festivals around Indonesia. Gojek would set up a large outdoor area that will be filled with their merchants, which would bring merchants that were previously located beyond the reach of customers in certain areas closer to them, so GoFood drivers are able to provide the discounted delivery services, and customers can also benefit from getting direct discounts doing the transaction through the Gojek app on the spot. To stay relevant to today's customers' behaviors, LEO Indonesia should also consider starting to be active and engaging on their own TikTok account as soon as possible. According to DataIndonesia.id (2022), the active monthly users of TikTok in Indonesia is currently the second largest in the world after the United States, reaching 99.1 million people in April 2022 out of the 191.4 million social media users in Indonesia. Even though this set of data is users over the age of 18, TikTok is also the only social media that allows marketers to target ads to users aged as young as 13 (Kemp, 2021). Therefore, by being active and advertising on TikTok, LEO will open to the much larger audience of Indonesia. Apart from the online and offline IMC suggestions mentioned above, advertisements on the more traditional methods will also help in reaching the smaller percentage of target audiences. This may contribute to significant differences, due to the sheer size of Indonesia's population, where even the smallest percentage translates to considerably large numbers of potential customers. These more traditional methods include TV and radio advertisements, billboards, brochures, etc. However, these advertisements are usually considered among the more expensive options but would all be worth it in the effort of getting the message across all generations and social classes of Indonesia. Another factor that can contribute to LEO's success is collaboration with other services, and not just necessarily food services. Customers of all products and services have been seeing the benefits and simplicity that comes with digital payment options, where 159 million of the population have been making digital payments by 2022. Now, LEO's platform majorly serves as a reservation maker, and all payments are still done through the cashiers of merchants' restaurants. In fact, even the service charge that LEO collects at the end of every month, would have to be invoiced to their merchants. If LEO offers digital payment services, not only will it make it easier for customers, but also for LEO themselves. Almost 4 years after LEO's launch in JABODETABEK,

perhaps it is also time to consider expansion to other major cities like Medan, Surabaya, Bandung, etc. During its heyday before Covid-19, there were already many comments in LEO's Instagram, Facebook, as well as Apple's App Store, saying that they were waiting for LEO to be operational in their cities. It may be possible that, before the pandemic hits, LEO had already reached their maximum potential around JABODETABEK. The key is then, to become a major enough player within the industry that everyone will take notice, to produce high levels of inbound traffic of both customers and merchants.

5. CONCLUSION

Entering a market with a blue ocean product and/or service is probably the riskiest and scariest thing for a company to do. There are a lot of considerations for it to be successful in the real world, but if done correctly, will also give high returns to all stakeholders. While most companies focus on creating the best possible product and/or services to bring to the market, sometimes they forget to also think about how to market and advertise these products, which can make all their hard work go to waste. In terms of the service that LEO offers, it has seemed to fit the needs of the market. All the previous pains and gains that were experienced by customers, as well as restaurants, have been accommodated in the values that LEO created within their services, for all stakeholders. The win-win situation was felt heavily by customers, merchants, and LEO himself. In fact, even after the Covid-19 hits, the only thing hampering LEO's users is the fact that they were not able to dine-in due to movement restrictions programs put in place by the government. However, the slowing down of interest in LEO, and their overall performance, happened also because of Covid-19. It might have made more sense for them to go into some sort of a safe mode by focusing on customer retention, but they should not have stayed in that safe zone that long. Even if foot traffic decreased heavily, and people stopped dining in, LEO should have prepared to regain their market presence the moment things started to look up. They should not have gone to the extent of stopping all sorts of customer acquisition efforts, as it has proven to put out the fire over the hype and awareness that they have previously succeeded in creating. Now that the economy and most other conditions have gone back to normal, it seems like LEO is restarting all over again. However, LEO now has the knowledge that their business model was already able to disrupt the food services industry beforehand. All they need now is to catch back up, by applying a more rigorous and aggressive Integrated Marketing Communications strategy to try and win back the hearts of their merchants and customers, taking care of the existing ones, as well as grabbing the attention of many new ones.

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